

MERICS CHINA FORECAST 2025

Survey results

Number of participants: 843

The survey was conducted online in November-December 2024

POLITICO

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HORIZONS
DEALING WITH A RESURGENT CHINA

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Mercator Institute for China Studies

Part 1: China's Domestic Development

Doubts on China's outlook for economic growth in 2025

Q1: What do you think how much China's economy will grow in 2025?

Real estate sector and weak consumption as risks for growth

Q2: In your view, which of the following are significant risks for China's growth outlook in 2025?

Domestic issues: focus on public order and ideological control

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Q3: In your view, what level of importance do you expect the Chinese Communist Party leadership to give to the following domestic issues in 2025?

Economic issues as likely sources of protests

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Q4: In your view, which of the following pressure points are likely to see public dissent and/or protests in 2025?

Mixed views on Chinese leadership's top priority

Q5: Which course of action do you see China's leadership taking up as their top priority in 2025?

China's innovation capabilities expected to improve

Q6: What is your overall outlook on how China's innovation capabilities will develop in 2025?

Decoupling regarded as risk for China's r&d progress

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Q7: In your view, which of the following are significant risks for China's research and development progress in 2025?

Part 2: Foreign policy & EU-China relations

China to enhance cooperation with non-Western partners

Q8: What do you think how China's foreign policy will develop in 2025?

Slight deterioration expected for China's relationship with EU

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Q9: In your view, how will China's relations with the EU and its member states develop in 2025?

* Weighted Average. Each category is assigned a score ranging from 1 (Deteriorate considerably) to 5 (Improve considerably). A score of 3 represents no changes.

Mixed expectations for China's relations with non-EU states

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Q10: In your view, how will China's relations with key non-EU states develop in 2025?

* Weighted Average. Each category is assigned a score ranging from 1 (Deteriorate considerably) to 5 (Improve considerably). A score of 3 represents no changes.

Mixed views on trajectory of China's support for Russia's war

Q11: In your view, how will China's relationship with Russia develop in 2025 in the context of Russia's war against Ukraine?

Chinese FDI to increase in Europe's EV sector

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Q12: How do you expect Chinese investment in Europe to evolve in 2025?

Downturn in political relations between EU and China

Q13: How do you expect EU-China relations to evolve in 2025?

- N/A
- Improve considerably
- Somewhat improve
- No changes
- Somewhat deteriorate
- Deteriorate considerably

EU-China cooperation likely in fight against climate change

Q14: In 2025, in which areas are the EU and its member states likely to make significant progress with regard to cooperation opportunities with China? Select up to 3 answers.

China and Trump: EU should balance and diversify partnerships

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Q15: In 2025, when it comes to transatlantic cooperation on China under the Trump administration, the EU and the majority of its member states should prioritize in their transatlantic agenda on China:

US-China relations: trade war, export controls, and decoupling

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Q16: How do you expect China-US relations to develop in 2025 under the Trump administration?

US' Taiwan policy: urge Taiwanese chip investments in US

Q17: How do you expect US policy toward Taiwan under the Trump administration to develop in 2025?

Part 3: About participants of the survey

Number of participants: 843

Europe (75%), US (7%), China (4.3%), Rest of the world (12%)

About participants of the survey

Statistics (age, gender, education, affiliation)

- Under 18
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+
- Prefer not to say

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Other (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

Education

Affiliation

Contact

MERICS | Mercator Institute for China Studies

Alte Jakobstraße 85-86

10179 Berlin

Tel.: +49 30 3440 999 0

Mail: info@merics.de

www.merics.org

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